

TABLE-2

2, 6-DIARYL-5, 6-DIHYDRO-4H-1, 3-THIAZINES

No.	R	R ₁	M.P./B.P. °C.	HCl M.P., °C.	Molecular Formula	%N		%S	
						Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	H	H	86-87 ^a	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ NS	—	—	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	110 ^a	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NS	—	—	—	—
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	65	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	4.84	4.95	11.22	11.31
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	96 ^a	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClNS	—	—	—	—
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	H	91-92	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrNS	4.13	4.22	9.58	9.64
6.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	H	107-108	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NO ₂ S	4.61	4.71	10.69	10.77
7.	-H	-CH ₃	103-105/760 mm.	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NS.HCl	4.54	4.62	10.50	10.56
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-CH ₃	242-760 mm	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NS.HCl	4.34	4.41	10.04	10.09
9.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-CH ₃	239-41/760 mm	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ .HCl	4.10	4.21	9.55	9.60
10.	<i>p</i> -Cl	-CH ₃	228/760 mm	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNS.HCl	4.07	4.14	9.41	9.47
11.	<i>p</i> -Br	-CH ₃	236/760 mm	89-90	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrNS.HCl	3.54	3.66	8.31	8.37
12.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	-CH ₃	78-80	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	4.38	4.50	10.19	10.29
13.	-H	-OCH ₃	85	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₂	4.85	4.95	11.23	11.31
14.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-OCH ₃	230/760 mm	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ .HCl	4.11	4.21	9.54	9.60
15.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-OCH ₃	239-40/760 mm	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NO ₂ .S.HCl	3.92	4.01	9.09	9.16
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl	-OCH ₃	227/760 mm	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNOS.HCl	3.86	3.97	8.99	9.04
17.	<i>p</i> -Br	-OCH ₃	237-38/760 mm	81	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrNOS.HCl	3.40	3.52	7.96	8.04
18.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	-OCH ₃	88-89	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S	4.16	4.28	9.70	9.79
19.	-H	-Cl	227/760 mm	82-83	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClNS.HCl	4.22	4.33	9.84	9.88
20.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	-Cl	230-31/760 mm	93-95	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNS.HCl	4.05	4.14	9.40	9.47
21.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	-Cl	232/760 mm	80-81	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClNOS.HCl	3.88	3.97	8.98	9.04
22.	<i>p</i> -Cl	-Cl	213/760 mm	88	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ NS.HCl	3.81	3.91	8.90	8.93
23.	<i>p</i> -Br	-Cl	226/760 mm	82-84	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrClNS.HCl	3.39	3.48	7.88	7.94
24.	3, 4-Methylenedioxy.	-Cl	76	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂ S	4.13	4.23	9.59	9.66

^a Reported by C. Giordano, *Synthesis*, 1972, No. 1, 34-35.

solution washed with 2N HCl (2 × 50 ml) at ~ 10° and acid extract made alkaline by 40% aq. alkali. This was extracted with ether and after drying ethereal solution, it gave on evaporation thiazines (vide Table 2). If the product was liquid, it was isolated as hydrochloride. Yields were in the range of 30 to 50%.

I.R. Spectra of all these thiazines show absorption band at 1634-1600 cm⁻¹ typical of C=N linkage present in dihydro-1, 3-thiazines as reported earlier⁴. Mol. Weights of first three were checked by their mass spectra.

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Synthesis of 3-Phenylsulphonamido-4-methoxybenzoic Acid Hydrazide and their Derivatives

H. E. MASTER and V. V. NADKARNY

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-400 001

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IN continuation of the work done by us on hydrazides and their derivatives as antibacterial agents^{1,2} we extend the work to 3-phenylsulphonamido-4-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide. The hydrazide was synthesised and various N-benzylidene derivatives were prepared by condensing it with aromatic aldehydes. Condensation of the hydrazide with isothiocyanates yielded the thiosemicarbazides which were cyclised to 3,4-disubstituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-4H triazole³.

Experimental

3-Chlorosulphonylamisic acid was prepared in 64% yield by the chlorosulphonation of anisic acid using 6 moles of chlorosulphonic acid at 65-70^o, m.p. 178^o. (Found : C, 38.44 ; H, 3.0 ; S, 12.58 ;

NOTES

TABLE 1—N-BENZYLIDENE-3-PHENYLSULPHONAMIDO-4-METHOXYBENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDE

No.	Ar	M.P. °C	% Yield	Molecular Formula	% Analysis			
					Found	N	Reqd.	Found
1.	C ₆ H ₅	268	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	10.50	10.27	7.95	7.82
2.	2-HOC ₆ H ₄	291	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.91	9.88	7.59	7.53
3.	4-HOC ₆ H ₄	287	73	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.79	9.88	7.68	7.53
4.	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	308	79	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.77	9.67	7.33	7.29
5.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	283	67	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	12.90	12.33	6.98	7.05
6.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	273	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.38	9.23	7.10	7.03
7.	2-Furyl	284	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S	10.20	10.52	8.35	8.02

TABLE 2—1-(3'-PHENYLSULPHONAMIDO-4'-METHOXYPHENYL) AROYL-4-ARYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDE

No.	Ar	M.P. °C	% Yield	Molecular Formula	% Analysis			
					Found	N	Reqd.	Found
8.	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	217	91.5	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Br	10.5	10.47	12.03	11.96
9.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	208	85.0	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	12.0	11.91	13.66	13.61
10.	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	209	89.0	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	11.32	11.43	13.17	13.06
11.	1-Naphthyl	161	81.0	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	11.1	11.07	12.71	12.65

TABLE 3—3-(3'-PHENYLSULPHONAMIDO-4'-METHOXYPHENYL)-4-ARYL-5-MERCAPTO-1, 2, 4-4H TRIAZOLE

No.	Ar	M.P. °C	% Yield	Molecular Formula	% Analysis			
					Found	N	Reqd.	Found
12.	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	275	86	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Br	11.00	10.83	12.31	12.38
13.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	263	84	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	12.48	12.39	14.18	14.16
14.	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	281	87	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	11.80	11.87	13.41	13.56
15.	1-Naphthyl	291	77	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	11.45	11.48	13.00	13.12

Cl, 14.0%. Calcd for C₈H₇O₅SCl : C, 38.31 ; H, 2.79 ; S, 12.8 ; Cl, 14.2%.

3-Phenylsulphonamido-4-methoxybenzoic acid was prepared using molar amounts of aniline with pyridine as a base m.p. 235° (crystallised from ethanol) yield 66% (Found : C, 54.2 ; H, 4.35 ; N, 4.55 ; S, 10.48%. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃O₅NS : C, 54.73 ; H, 4.23 ; N, 4.56 ; S, 10.42%).

The methyl ester m.p. 176° (crystallised from ethanol) yield 78% (Found : C, 55.91 ; H, 4.80 ; N, 4.30 ; S, 10.2%. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₅O₅NS : C,

56.08 ; H, 4.67 ; N, 4.36 ; S, 9.97%), and the hydrazone m.p. 108° (crystallised from ethanol) yield 83% (Found : C, 52.19 ; H, 4.61 ; N, 13.0 ; S, 10.03%. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₅O₄N₂S : C, 52.34 ; H, 4.67 ; N, 13.08 ; S, 9.97%) were prepared in the usual manner.

The N-benzylidene derivatives (Table 1), 1-(3'-phenylsulphonamido-4'-methoxyphenyl)-aroyl-4-aryl thiosemicarbazide (Table 2) and 3-(3'-phenylsulphonamido-4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-4H triazoles (Table 3) were prepared in the usual manner⁶.

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Chemical Constituents of *Polypodium amoenum* Wall

ASOK DASGUPTA and H. N. KHASTGIR*

Department of Chemistry,

University of North Bengal, Darjeeling

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POLYPODIUM amoenum (Polypodiaceae) grow in the Himalayan region at an altitude 4,000-11,000 ft and also from Garhwal to Bhutan, very common in Khasia range (altitude 3,000-6,000 ft). The present communication describes the isolation of fern-9(11)-ene²⁻³, hop-22(29)-ene⁴⁻⁶ and β -sitosterol from the whole plant.

Benzene extract of the dried powdered fern was separated into acid and neutral fractions. The latter was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petrol (60-80°) yielded a waxy solid which was found by TLC (12% AgNO₃ impregnated silicagel) to be a mixture of two components. On rechromatography over silicagel (E. Merck) impregnated with AgNO₃ followed by crystallisation (chloroform : methanol) it afforded two hydrocarbons A and B having the same mol. formula C₃₀H₅₀(M⁺410).

Compound A (found C, 88.01, H, 12.15) m.p. 166-68° [α_D]CHCl₃ - 16.1° showed significant peaks at m/e 257, 243, 231 in its mass spectrum similar to those recorded for fern-9(11)-ene. Its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p, IR and Co-TLC).

Compound B (found C, 87.59, H, 12.42), m.p. 210-11°, [α_D]CHCl₃ + 61°. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 880 cm⁻¹ (>C=CH₂) was found to be identical (m.m.p, IR, MS) with hop-22(29)-ene (Diploptene).

Further elution of the column with petrol : benzene (3 : 2) furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 133-36°, [α_D]CHCl₃ - 32°, acetate, m.p. 126-28°, [α_D]CHCl₃ - 38°, identical with authentic specimens.

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Coumarins from *Pimpinella diversifolia*

CHANDER B. BHATIA, S. K. BANERJEE* and K. L. HANDA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu-Tawi-180001

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P. diversifolia (Umbelliferae) is a herb growing in the north-western Himalayan region. No work on this plant has so far been reported. From the aerial parts of this plant two coumarins have been isolated and identified as ammirin (isoangomalin) and oxypeucedanin on the basis of IR, NMR, MS and TLC data.

The petroleum ether extract of the air dried, powdered aerial parts (2 Kg) of the plant yielded a dark green residue (30 g) which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (grade IV). Elution with petroleum ether gave a mixture of hydrocarbons, m.p. 77-78°. The earlier benzene eluates on chromatography over silica gel followed by PLC afforded ammirin (44 mg) in needles (benzene-acetone), m.p. 110-12° (lit^a, m.p. 117°), blue fluorescence under UV. NMR (90 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.79(3H, s, methyl), 3.27 (2H, dq, J 16, 8Hz, H-3'), 4.98(1H, br s) and 5.13 (1H, br s)-olefinic protons, 5.32 (1H, t, J 8Hz, H-2'), 6.23 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 6.78 (1H, s, H-8), 7.30 (1H, s, H-5), 7.62 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4). MS : Ion peaks at m/e 228 (M⁺), 213, 185 among others.

Later fractions of benzene eluates from silica gel chromatography, on purification by PLC, afforded oxypeucedanin (20 mg), m.p. 144-45° (lit.^a m.p. 142-43°), M⁺ 286. IR and NMR spectra were in concordance with those of an authentic sample.

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